

Dielectric and excess dielectric constants of binary liquid mixtures : Chlorobenzene + nitrobenzene, cyclohexanone + nitrobenzene and benzene + nitrobenzene at 303 K

Ch. V. V. Ramana and K. Malakondaiah*

Scientific Instrumentation Laboratory, Department of Instrumentation & University Science Instrumentation Centre, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur-515 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : ramana6@gmail.com

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Abstract : The nonideal behaviour of liquid mixtures are characterized by excess thermodynamic properties such as excess volumes, enthalpy of mixing, compressibilities etc. The excess dielectric constant ϵ^E is also one such parameter that indicates the strength and nature of intermolecular interactions in binary liquid mixtures. The positive deviations from ideal behaviour (ϵ^E being positive) are qualitatively attributed to a "build in" of components of the mixture in the structure of respective solvent. The negative deviations from ideal behaviour (ϵ^E being negative) is explained qualitatively either due to interstitial solvation or due to breaking of aggregates. In the present study, the excess dielectric constants for the binary liquid mixtures (1) benzene + nitrobenzene, (2) chlorobenzene + nitrobenzene and (3) cyclohexanone + nitrobenzene are measured at 303 K and at different concentrations. The dielectric constants for these binary liquid mixtures are measured using a computer based system. It is based on the principle that the change in frequency of XR-2206 function generator, when the liquid forms the dielectric medium of the dielectric cell, is measured with a personal computer. The programmable interval timer 8254 available in the DIOT card is used to measure the frequency which in turn determines the capacitance of the cell and dielectric constant. The necessary software is developed in C language.

Keywords : Dielectric constants, excess dielectric constants.

Introduction

Dielectric studies have a long and distinguished history. The dielectric data is used to determine the electric dipole moments, which is not only significant as a reflection of electronic structure of the molecule, but is also of prime importance in understanding of molecular interactions and it at least partly controls the transitions between the solid, liquid and gaseous states. The dielectric constant ϵ of a liquid is defined as the ratio of the electrical capacitance of a cell when the liquid/solution forms the dielectric medium (C_s) to the capacitance of the cell when air forms the dielectric medium (C_0) at a given temperature, which is represented by the following equation,

$$\epsilon = (C_s)/(C_0) \quad (1)$$

The dielectric cell consists of two parallel metallic plates which act as electrodes. The cell acts as a capacitor while

the liquid acts as a dielectric medium. The cell has to be first standardized by a pure liquid such as benzene to measure the dielectric constant of unknown solutions. The dielectric constant of an unknown liquid (ϵ_x) can be determined by measuring the capacitance of the cell in air (C_0), the capacitance of cell in reference liquid (C_r) such as benzene and the capacitance of the cell in liquid whose dielectric constant has to be measured (C_x) using the relation,

$$\epsilon_x = 1 + [(C_0 - C_x)/(C_0 - C_r)] \times (\epsilon_r - 1) \quad (2)$$

where ϵ_r is the dielectric constant of the reference liquid.

The excess dielectric constant ϵ^E is defined as,

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon^E &= \epsilon_{\text{observed}} - \epsilon_{\text{ideal}} \\ \epsilon^E &= \epsilon_{12} - (\epsilon_1 X_1 + \epsilon_2 X_2) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where ϵ_{12} is dielectric constant of the binary liquid mix-

ture. ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are the dielectric constants of solvent and solute respectively. X_1 and X_2 are mole fractions of solvent and solute respectively. The positive deviations from ideal behaviour (ϵ^E being positive) are qualitatively attributed to a "build in" of components of the mixture in the structure of respective solvent. The negative deviations from ideal behaviour (ϵ^E being negative) is explained qualitatively either due to interstitial solvation or due to breaking of aggregates¹. The excess dielectric constant ϵ^E is one of the parameters that indicates the strength and nature of intermolecular interactions in binary liquid mixtures and the nature of solute-solvent interactions.

Experimental

In the present paper analytical reagent grade samples were used after necessary purification and distillation mostly as per procedure cited by Weissberger². The chemicals used were benzene, chlorobenzene, cyclohexanone and nitrobenzene. Benzene was allowed to stand on anhydrous calcium chloride for two days and then filtered. Then the liquid was refluxed with phosphorus pentoxide for six hours and distilled. Spectroscopically pure sodium was drawn in wires in the distillate and redistilled. The liquid was collected at its boiling point 80 °C. The densities and the dielectric constants of the pure liquids at 303 K agreed within ± 0.002 and ± 0.2 with the corresponding literature values. A computer based dielectric constant system for the measurement of dielectric constant in liquids using XR-2206 function generator³ which operates at 1 MHz, was used for determination of the dielectric constants. The dielectric cell consists of two circular discs (25 mm diameter) of brass metal, whose faces are well machined and later polished with fine emery. The two conducting plates are positioned parallel to each other at close proximity by two brass leads of about 3 mm diameter which are connected to a thick circular hylam sheet of diameter 50 mm. The length of leads is kept as small as possible (2.5 cm). These leads form interconnections between BNC (SRF-10 recepticle of 50 Ω impedance) and the two conducting circular plates of the capacitor. It offers a capacitance of 25 pf approximately. The design of dielectric cell for use with solutions is made such that the structure of the cell is rigid so that the

variation of its capacitance due to strain is negligible and also it is less fragile. The filling and emptying of the cell is made as quickly as possible.

Results and discussion

The system is used to measure the dielectric constant of binary liquid mixtures (1) benzene + nitrobenzene, (2) chlorobenzene + nitrobenzene and (3) cyclohexanone + nitrobenzene at 303 K and at different concentrations (mole/L). The measurements are made following the procedure mentioned above. The results of measurements for these systems are presented in Table 1. And also the results are presented graphically as shown in Fig. 1. It is observed that at a given temperature the dielectric constant varies as a function of concentration for all the three binary liquid mixtures.

Table 1. Dielectric constants of the binary liquid mixtures at 303 K

Mole fraction (X_1)	Dielectric constant (ϵ)		
	Benzene + nitrobenzene	Chlorobenzene + nitrobenzene	Cyclohexanone + nitrobenzene
0.0	34.89	5.96	17.96
0.2	26.13	10.56	21.04
0.4	16.92	15.76	24.08
0.6	12.32	22.18	27.63
0.8	7.26	28.51	31.27
1.0	2.26	34.89	34.89

Fig. 1. Dielectric constant for three binary liquid mixtures versus concentration at 303 K.

The excess dielectric constants for the above binary liquid mixtures were evaluated using the eq. (3). The results of the ϵ^E measurements are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Excess dielectric constants of the binary liquid mixtures at 303 K

Mole fraction (X_1)	Excess dielectric constant (ϵ^E)		
	Nitrobenzene + chlorobenzene	Nitrobenzene + cyclohexanone	Benzene + nitrobenzene
0.0	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.2	-1.186	-0.306	-2.236
0.4	-1.772	-0.652	-4.919
0.6	-1.138	-0.488	-2.994
0.8	-0.594	-0.228	-1.524
1.0	0.000	0.000	0.000

The variation of ϵ^E as a function of concentration is graphically represented in Fig. 2. Observation of variation of ϵ^E with X_1 in all three binary mixtures indicates that they are negative and large in magnitude. The negative and large values of ϵ^E may be attributed to the dense solution structure⁴. The excess dielectric constant varies as a function of concentration and reaches an optimum ratio in the concentration range $X_1 = 0.3$ to 0.45 indicates the extent of intermolecular interactions in binary liquid mixtures.

Fig. 2. Excess dielectric constant for three binary liquid mixtures versus concentration at 303 K.**References**

1. P. Rohdewald and M. Moldner, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1973, **77**, 373.
2. A. Weissberger (ed.), "Technique of Organic Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1967, Vol. III.
3. XR-2206 function generator chip Datasheet, 1.997, EXAR the analog plus company.
4. V. Fried, L. P. Miller and H. Wachter, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1977, **50**, 497.